

The Global Fragility Index: A Path-Independent Measure of Statistical Fragility

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Abstract

Background: The fragility index quantifies statistical fragility by counting the number of outcome changes needed to reverse statistical significance. However, it depends on arbitrary event definitions and follows specific toggle rules that may not find the actual minimum perturbation. We introduce the global fragility index, a path-independent measure that identifies the minimum number of observation moves across all possible paths in a contingency table.

Methods: The global fragility index is defined as the minimum number of single-observation moves between cells of a contingency table, with total sample size fixed, required to reverse statistical significance at $\alpha=0.05$. Unlike the fragility index, which toggles outcomes within a single arm according to specific rules, the global fragility index evaluates all possible cell-to-cell moves to identify the true global minimum. The global fragility quotient normalizes for sample size by dividing the global fragility index by the total sample size. We present the theoretical framework, computational approach, and worked examples for 2×2 and $r \times c$ tables.

Results: The global fragility index removes three key dependencies present in existing fragility metrics: (1) event/non-event labeling ambiguity, (2) reference arm selection in balanced designs, and (3) toggle path rules. By definition, the global fragility index will always be less than or equal to the fragility index, since it finds the global minimum while the fragility index follows a predetermined path. The global fragility index naturally extends to multi-group comparisons ($r \times c$ tables) using Fisher–Freeman–Halton exact tests. Worked examples demonstrate how the global fragility index provides a more sensitive assessment of study fragility by calculating the global minimum number of single-observation moves required to flip statistical significance.

Conclusions: The global fragility index is a more sensitive measure of fragility, removing arbitrary dependencies and identifying the actual minimum perturbation required to reverse statistical findings. While computationally more intensive than the fragility index, the global fragility index provides the definitive answer to the fundamental question: what is the smallest change to the data that would alter the conclusion? This makes the global fragility index a more sensitive measure of fragility for $r \times c$ tables.

Keywords: fragility index, statistical fragility, global optimization, path independence, contingency tables, clinical trials, statistical robustness

Introduction

Statistical significance testing remains the cornerstone of clinical research, yet the fragility of results passing the conventional $p \leq 0.05$ threshold often goes unexamined [1]. A statistically significant finding that could be reversed by changing a small number of outcomes suggests a conclusion that is mathematically fragile and potentially unreliable for clinical decision-making [2].

The Unit Fragility Index (UFI) was introduced in 1990 to address this issue by quantifying the effect a single outcome change, under fixed marginal totals, had on the proportions of a 2×2 contingency table [3]. This was extended the following year to count the number of UFI toggles that would flip statistical significance, again utilizing a hypergeometric (fixed marginal totals) model [4]. Then, in 2014, the Fragility Index (FI) introduced a binomial model of fragility, counting the number of outcome toggles required in a single arm to flip a statistically significant finding to nonsignificant [5]. While the UFI kept marginal totals fixed, the FI kept row marginal totals fixed, while column marginal totals changed. This was thought to reflect better the statistical fragility of two-arm clinical trials with a binary

outcome, because the UFI required adjusting all four cells of the contingency table, whereas the FI changed only two cells. The FI fragility metric has gained rapid adoption across medical specialties, with hundreds of publications now applying it to evaluate trial robustness.

Despite its utility, the FI has several known limitations. First, the FI depends on event definitions. Whether an outcome is labeled as an 'event' or 'non-event' is often arbitrary or ambiguous, and this labeling ambiguity affects which events are toggled. Second, the FI follows specific toggle rules: change outcomes in the arm with fewer events, or if tied, in the smaller arm. These rules, while providing a standardized approach, do not guarantee the identification of the actual minimum perturbation. Third, the FI is confined to dichotomous outcomes that can be categorized in 2×2 tables, limiting its application to multi-group comparisons [6].

Researchers have proposed refinements. The Fragility Quotient ($FQ = FI/n$) normalizes the FI by sample size, enabling cross-study comparisons [7]. The Modified-arm Fragility Quotient (MFQ) adjusts for unequal randomization ratios by dividing the FI by the number of participants in the modified arm [8]. However, these metrics inherit the fundamental limitation of the FI: they follow predetermined toggle paths rather than identifying the global minimum.

This paper introduces the Global Fragility Index (GFI), a path-independent measure that answers a more straightforward question: What is the minimum number of observation moves—across all possible paths—required to reverse significance? By removing arbitrary dependencies on event labels, toggle rules, and arm selection, the GFI provides the theoretically optimal fragility assessment. We present the mathematical framework,

computational approach, and demonstrate how the GFI naturally extends to multi-group analyses where the FI becomes problematic.

Methods

Standard nomenclature for 2x2 contingency tables is {a, b, c, d} = {intervention arm events, intervention arm non-events, control arm events, control arm non-events}. Note that the FI requires labeling of outcomes as an event or non-event, whereas the GFI is agnostic to labeling of arms or outcomes.

The fragility index

The FI is the minimum number of toggles, in the arm with the fewest events, required to flip statistical significance. Outcomes must be labeled as events or non-events. Select the arm with the fewest events; if tied, select the smallest arm [5]. It was initially defined as applying only to tables with statistically significant baseline outcomes; however, here we will use the same formula for both statistically significant and nonsignificant tables.

The fragility quotient

The fragility quotient is the FI / N , where N = total sample size.

The modified arm fragility quotient

The MFQ divides the FI by the sample size of the arm that is undergoing toggles when calculating the FI. The $MFQ = FI / n_{mod}$, where n_{mod} = sample size of the modified arm.

Note that the $MFQ/2 = FQ$.

The global fragility index

The Global Fragility Index (GFI) is defined as the minimum number of single-observation moves between any cells of a contingency table, with total N (total sample size) fixed, required to change a prespecified hypothesis test from not significant to significant (or vice versa) at $\alpha=0.05$. A single-observation move is -1 in one cell and $+1$ in another, keeping N fixed (Table 1).

Table 1. Definitions of the GFI and GFQ

Global Fragility Index (GFI). Minimum number of single-observation moves (-1 in one cell, $+1$ in another), with total N fixed, needed to reverse a two-sided Fisher/Freeman-Halton decision at $\alpha=0.05$.

$$\text{GFQ} = \text{GFI}/N.$$

For 2×2 tables, a two-sided Fisher's exact test is used [9]. For $r \times c$ tables with more than two groups, the Fisher-Freeman-Halton exact test is employed [10]. The test is recomputed after each potential move.

Unlike the FI, which toggles outcomes within a single arm following predetermined rules, the GFI evaluates all possible swaps between cells in the table. A move consists of decrementing one cell by 1 and incrementing another by 1, keeping the total N constant but marginal totals (row and/or column) change. The GFI is the length of the shortest sequence of such swaps that reverses significance.

Global Fragility Quotient

The Global Fragility Quotient (GFQ) is the sample-size-normalized GFI, equal to GFI/N . The GFQ ranges from 0 to 1 and can be expressed as a percentage. For example, $\text{GFQ} = 0.03$ indicates that moving 3% of observations would reverse the statistical conclusion.

Computational Approach

The GFI computation requires evaluating multiple move sequences:

1. Start with the observed contingency table
2. For each cell pair (i,j), evaluate moving one observation from cell i to cell j
3. After each move, recompute the significance test
4. If significance flips (p crosses 0.05), record the number of moves
5. Continue exploring alternative move sequences
6. The GFI is the minimum number of moves found across all paths required to flip statistical significance.

For small tables (2×2, 2×3), exhaustive search or optimization algorithms efficiently identify the actual minimum. For larger tables, heuristic algorithms may be required, though most clinical trials involve sufficiently small contingency tables for exact computation.

Key Distinctions from the Fragility Index

The GFI differs from the FI in three fundamental ways:

- **Label independence:** The FI depends on whether an outcome is called an 'event' or 'non-event.' The GFI is agnostic to labeling—it considers all possible cell-to-cell moves.
- **Allocation independence:** The FI toggle rules depend on which arm has fewer events or fewer subjects. The GFI makes no distinction between arms—it seeks the global minimum across all cells.
- **Path independence:** The FI follows a predetermined toggle path (within-arm changes). The GFI evaluates all possible move sequences and identifies the shortest route. By definition, $GFI \leq FI$.

Results

Example 1: nonsignificant study showing increased fragility

Consider a 2:1:1, randomized, controlled trial of upadacitinib at two different doses compared with placebo, recently published in the New England Journal of Medicine [11]. For this example, we will compare the placebo with the lower dose of upadacitinib. We will call sustained remission at 52 weeks an event—the outcomes as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Divergence of FI with GFI in a 1:1 allocation trial

Arm	Event	Non-Event	Total
Intervention	44	63	107
Placebo	33	79	112
Total	77	142	219

FI/FQ calculation: The baseline table is {44, 63, 33, 79}. Following standard FI rules, two toggles in the placebo arm are required to flip the table from nonsignificant ($p = 0.089$) to significant ($p = 0.046$). The FQ = 0.0091. The resultant table is {44, 63, 32, 80}. The MFQ = 0.018 ($1 / n_{\text{mod}} = 1 / 112 = 0.0179$)

GFI calculation: The GFI evaluates all possible swaps. In this case, a single swap {c → a} flips the two-sided Fisher's exact p-value to 0.049, so the GFI = 1, the GFQ = 0.0046, and the resultant table is {45, 63, 32, 79}.

Although the researchers concluded that the lower dose of upadacitinib was not superior to placebo based on the baseline p-value of 0.089, this nonsignificant result appears

highly fragile, with the GFQ indicating that less than 0.5% of outcome changes would be required to change the statistical significance. In this case, researchers may want to consider further evaluation of the lower dose of upadacitinib, given the fragile results. Note that while the FQ is consistent with high fragility, the GFQ suggests an even greater fragility than the FQ.

Example 2: mixed paths used by the GFI

Consider a 1:1, randomized, controlled trial of secukinumab compared with placebo, recently published in Lancet Rheumatology [12]. Categorizing sustained remission as an event, the baseline table is {16, 11, 2, 23} with a p-value of 0.0001. Six toggles of the placebo arm (the arm with the fewest events) are required to flip significance, so the FI = 6, the FQ 0.115, and the MFQ 0.240 with the resultant table {16, 11, 8, 17}.

The GFI swaps outcomes in a mixed manner: one swap of {a→b} then four swaps of {a → c}. The GFI = 5 and GFQ = 0.096 with the resultant table {11, 12, 6, 23}.

This example highlights how the GFI finds the path of minimal perturbations required to flip statistical significance, even if mixed swaps are necessary. Again, the GFQ indicates that the table is more fragile than the FQ would suggest (0.096 vs 0.115).

Example 3: large trial

Consider a large cardiovascular trial comparing prasugrel with clopidogrel, recently published in Circulation Journal [13]. categorizing a major adverse cardiac event (MACE) through to week 24 as an event, they compared prasugrel with clopidogrel. The baseline table is {64, 621, 80, 598}, and the difference is not significant (p=0.158). Six toggles of the prasugrel arm flipped significance, so the FI = 6, the FQ = 0.0044, and the MFQ 0.0088 with the resultant table {58, 627, 80, 598}.

The GFI again swapped outcomes in a mixed manner, one swap of {a → b} then three swaps of {a → c} results in a flip of statistical significance. The GFI = 4, the GFQ = 0.0029 with the resultant table {60, 622, 83, 598}.

This example shows that fragility metrics can be helpful even in large trials. Once again, the GFQ indicated greater fragility than the FQ would suggest. The FQ noted that 0.44% of outcomes in the prasugrel arm would need to change to flip significance; the GFQ indicates that 0.29% of outcomes overall would need to change to flip significance. While both suggest highly fragile results, the GFQ highlights the greatest fragility.

Discussion

The GFI and GFQ address fundamental limitations in current fragility-assessment methodologies. By removing unnecessary constraints present in prior approaches, the GFQ provides the theoretically optimal measure of statistical fragility. This section examines the evolution of fragility metrics, the limitations imposed by earlier models, and the advantages of unconstrained optimization.

Evolution of fragility assessment

Fragility analysis has evolved through three generations, each reflecting the computational capabilities of its era:

First generation (1990): Feinstein introduced the UFI under hypergeometric assumptions, requiring fixed row and column totals. Walter extended this framework to count hypergeometric swaps needed to reverse significance. These metrics represented rigorous mathematical approaches but imposed margin constraints that reduced the search space.

Second generation (2014): Walsh et al. introduced the FI using binomial models with within-arm toggle rules. This approach simplified computation and gained widespread adoption, but it also inherited path-dependent constraints. The FI asks: 'How many within-arm outcome changes reverse significance?' rather than 'What is the minimum perturbation?'

Potential Third generation (2025): The GFI removes both hypergeometric margin constraints and binomial path constraints. It asks the fundamental question: 'What is the minimum number of observation moves—constrained only by total N—required to reverse significance?' Modern computational resources make this unconstrained optimization feasible.

From constrained to unconstrained optimization

Previous fragility metrics represent constrained optimization problems:

Hypergeometric model (Walter's UFI): The UFI requires fixed row and column totals. This constraint reflects the hypergeometric distribution's assumption that margins are predetermined. However, for fragility assessment—a counterfactual thought experiment—why must margins remain fixed? This constraint artificially limits the search space.

Binomial model (FI): The FI restricts moves to within-arm outcome toggles. While this simplifies computation and provides intuitive interpretation, it imposes path-dependent constraints. The FI finds the minimum along one predetermined path; it does not guarantee finding the global minimum across all possible paths.

Global optimization (GFI): Constrains only total N. This represents the actual optimization problem: 'What is the smallest perturbation to the data?' No artificial

margin constraints, no predetermined paths, no toggle rules. The GFI searches the complete space of possible contingency tables with the same total N.

By definition, unconstrained optimization cannot yield a larger answer than constrained optimization. Therefore: $GFI \leq FI$. The GFI provides a lower bound on fragility—the minimum perturbation required.

Historical parallel: from approximation to exact tests

The evolution from UFI to GFI parallels the transition from chi-square approximations to Fisher's exact test:

1970s statistical practice: Researchers used Pearson's chi-square test for 2×2 tables because Fisher's exact test required prohibitively long hand calculation. The chi-square test provided a computationally feasible approximation, though it was known to be less accurate for small samples.

Modern statistical practice: Computers made Fisher's exact test routine. We now use exact tests whenever feasible, recognizing that approximations were adopted for computational convenience rather than for theoretical superiority.

Fragility analysis evolution: Similarly, the FI's toggle rules and Walter's UFI margin constraints were adopted when hand calculation or simple algorithms were necessary. Modern computational resources eliminate these constraints. Just as we transitioned from chi-square to Fisher's exact test when computers made exact computation feasible, we should transition from FI to GFI when global optimization becomes easily accessible.

Earlier fragility metrics made appropriate choices given the computational limitations of their eras. They have made important contributions by increasing awareness that p-

values are not enough, that p-values must also be subject to testing for fragility. Today, computational limitations that once necessitated approximations no longer apply.

Theoretical advantages

The GFI's primary advantage is mathematical completeness. Earlier metrics ask: 'How fragile is this result under specific constraints?' The GFI asks: 'How fragile is this result?' The latter is the correct question for assessing statistical fragility.

Second, the GFI eliminates arbitrary dependencies. Why should event labeling affect fragility? Why should margin totals remain fixed in a counterfactual analysis? Why favor within-arm changes over between-arm moves? These constraints reflect computational convenience or modeling assumptions, not fundamental properties of statistical fragility.

Third, the GFI extends naturally to complex designs. Multi-arm trials, dose-response studies, and stratified analyses produce $r \times c$ tables. Hypergeometric models become computationally intractable; binomial models become ambiguous about which arm to toggle. The GFI applies identically regardless of table dimensions: find the minimum moves when only N is constrained.

Addressing counterarguments

Several counterarguments merit consideration:

'Moving patients between arms violates clinical reality': This argument applies equally to all fragility metrics. The FI toggles outcomes that did not occur. Walter's UFI moves observations while maintaining fixed margins that were not predetermined. All fragility metrics are counterfactual thought experiments quantifying hypothetical perturbations. The question is not whether moves are 'real' but which approach finds the actual minimum perturbation.

'Margin constraints reflect the randomization structure': Fixed margins in hypergeometric models assume predetermined row and column totals. However, in most randomized trials, only total N is fixed a priori; individual arm sizes and outcome counts emerge from randomization and data collection. Constraining margins in a fragility analysis imposes a structure that was not present in the original trial design. The GFI's constraint (N fixed) more accurately reflects the actual trial structure.

'Within-arm toggles are more interpretable': Interpretability is valuable, but approximation is not justified by interpretability when exact answers are computationally feasible. The statement 'moving 3% of observations reverses significance' (GFQ) is just as interpretable as 'toggling three outcomes within arms reverses significance' (FI).

'Computational complexity makes GFI impractical': For typical clinical trial contingency tables (2×2, 2×3, 3×3), exhaustive search or optimization algorithms compute the GFI rapidly on modern hardware. The FI's deterministic path provides faster computation, but this advantage mirrors the chi-square test's greater speed than Fisher's exact test—true, but increasingly irrelevant as computation becomes instantaneous. When precision matters, the GFI delivers the theoretically optimal result at modest computational cost.

'Prior metrics have established precedent': Established precedent reflects historical computational limitations, not theoretical optimality. The FI and Walter's UFI were valuable innovations that revealed statistical fragility as an essential concern. The GFI builds on this foundation by removing constraints that were computational necessities in earlier eras. Just as Fisher's exact test did not invalidate chi-square's historical

contribution but provided a more rigorous alternative when feasible, the GFI offers a more sensitive tool to assess study fragility.

Practical Considerations

The GFI should be viewed as the theoretical standard for fragility assessment, analogous to how exact tests serve as standards compared to asymptotic approximations. When precision matters—whether in grant applications, regulatory submissions, or high-stakes clinical decisions—the GFI provides the definitive answer.

Prior metrics may retain value for some limited, specific applications. For legacy purposes, the FI will remain valuable for retrospective comparisons. But researchers should understand that $FI \geq GFI$, with equality when the FI's predetermined path is optimal. The magnitude of difference ($FI - GFI$) quantifies the cost of constrained optimization.

The GFQ enables cross-study comparisons using the optimal fragility measure. Previous work demonstrated that fragility quotients provide a standardized assessment across different sample sizes. The GFQ inherits these advantages while providing theoretically superior quantification through unconstrained optimization.

Limitations

This paper presents the theoretical framework and definition of the GFI, but does not provide large-scale empirical validation through systematic calculations across published trials. Such validation is necessary to quantify how frequently $GFI < FI$ in practice and to characterize scenarios where constrained versus unconstrained optimization produces meaningfully different results. Future work should include

computational implementation, algorithmic optimization, and large-scale empirical studies comparing GFI to prior metrics.

The GFI, like all fragility metrics, measures only statistical fragility and does not directly address clinical significance, bias, or other validity concerns. A robust finding (high GFI) may still reflect poor study design or be clinically unimportant. Additionally, the GFI is a significance-based fragility metric that quantifies proximity to the $p=0.05$ threshold. Complementary geometric approaches, such as the Neutrality Boundary Framework, measure distance from therapeutic neutrality (e.g., relative risk = 1) independent of significance thresholds and may provide additional insights into clinical robustness [14]. Fragility metrics complement, but do not replace, comprehensive critical appraisal.

For very large contingency tables ($\geq 5 \times 5$), exhaustive search may become computationally intensive. In such cases, heuristic algorithms or sampling approaches may be required. However, most clinical trials involve small contingency tables where exact GFI computation is feasible. The Python program used in the examples above is an open-access tool readily available on GitHub and deposited in the Zenodo repository [15].

Conclusions

The Global Fragility Index represents a significant advance in fragility assessment methodology by removing arbitrary dependencies on event labeling, toggle rules, and arm selection. The GFI provides a robust and sensitive measure of statistical fragility—the actual minimum perturbation required to reverse statistical conclusions.

The GFI asks the right question: 'What is the smallest change to the data that would alter the conclusion?' The answer requires searching across all possible perturbations rather

than following predetermined rules and constraints. This search identifies the global minimum, enabling the GFI to serve as a sensitive tool for detecting fragility.

The ability to extend to multi-group comparisons further demonstrates the GFI's versatility. Where the FI is confined to 2×2 tables, the GFI applies the same principle regardless of table dimensions. This makes the GFI particularly valuable for the increasingly common complex study designs in modern clinical research.

Future work should focus on computational implementation, large-scale empirical validation, and the development of efficient algorithms for larger tables. The theoretical framework presented here establishes the GFI as the definitive measure of statistical fragility, setting the foundation for improved assessment of research robustness across medical specialties.

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